

Pedagogy *With* Force-Feedback Interaction at Grenoble Alpes University-France

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Abstract. This article reports on the pedagogy that *make use* of Force Feedback and multisensory interaction to teach varied knowledge at Univ. Grenoble Alpes.

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1 The Enactive Learning pedagogical network

Since 2018, the Enactive Learning (*Apprentissage Enactif*) network of Univ. Grenoble Alpes joins 5 platforms equipped with multisensory interaction technology, virtual reality, including complementary force feedback technology. About 400 learners are impacted yearly, from pre-university vulgarization sessions to Bachelor, Master degree, and PhD, in varied disciplines (Engineering, Physics, product design, Arts, Computer-assisted surgery, ...). This article reports, with 2 examples, on 2 ongoing pedagogies that *make use* of force feedback to teach in a given field of knowledge (nanoscience and musicology), by rooting generally speaking on the principle of embodied cognition.

Fig. 1. Examples of the force-feedback powered VR stations of the CIME NanoWorld platform.

2 Pedagogy in Nanosciences and Nanotechnology

The Nanoworld platform of Grenoble's inter-university center for micro-electronics and nanotechnologies (CIME) has a pedagogical activity in Nanoscience and Nanophysics. In addition to optical and Atomic Force microscopes, the platform has developed for ~15 years, in collaboration with research and industrial groups, especially ACROE, 4 VR pedagogical stations. These stations focus on the principles of Atomic

Force Microscopy (AFM), and on how AFM enables mapping morphological and rheological properties of a sample down to atomic scale. Each station features force feedback (ERGOS, Omega.3 and Novint falcons), and several nanoscale VR scenes. See [1, 2, 3] for a technical description. They are used in pedagogy at Bachelor's, Master's, PhD degrees in Nanophysics, and also with high school students. We summarize their pedagogical relevance with more than 10 years of pedagogy experience as follows:

Trigger an embodied/enactive knowledge, in parallel to theoretical learning. Physical behaviors at micro and nanoscales are not accessible to sensorimotor experience. Using VR, especially force feedback and physical simulation, offers a unique possibility to build, for each student, tangible representations of the highly non-linear laws of micro- and nanophysics, and of how AFM works. An embodied knowledge is triggered. Besides, this modifies acquisition, and facilitates anchoring, of the associated theoretical knowledge. For example, students learn how to correlate their sensory-motor stimuli with the mechanical instabilities of AFM probes, which later facilitates comprehension and processing of real AFM data, when dealing with real AFMs [2].

New route to explore AFM data. Exploring AFM data is usually carried out by data-analysis, and somewhat standard visualizations (images and graphs). Adding haptics and VR considerably extends the possibilities. The *NanoEnactive* [3] station features virtual scenes set up from experimental data acquired by AFM on real samples, towards “digital twins” of real nanoobjects. By using this station, the students can comprehend and embody the rheological properties of the (simulated) real samples, by means of multisensory interaction.

Shorten pedagogical pathways. Changing an AFM probe, a sample, etc. in a real AFM is too time consuming to achieve in a teaching session. The *NanoMan* station implements algorithmic-based simulation of Nano-Physical laws. It enables exploring in a short time a large range of AFM situations, by simply changing parameters of the models: rheology of the virtual sample, tip-sample forces (Van der Waals or electromagnetic), medium (e.g. air vs water), elasticity of the virtual AFM probe, etc.

Trigger pedagogy in Computational Physical. Advanced students in NanoPhysics, at e.g. M2 or PhD levels, are proposed to reverse-engineer the multisensory stations. This develops acculturation of digital technologies for Physics students. Beyond, discussing the real time implementation of algorithmic formulations of Nanophysics laws opens innovative pedagogy in Computational Physics.

Motivate. Finally, the stations have an appeal for young people, as a sort of “serious game”. In our scientific vulgarization sessions, aimed at undergraduate students and non-physicists, the stations make the complex quantum and surface phenomena that occur at nanoscale during AFM-tips / surface interactions approachable. On their side, PhD students can trigger new exciting routes for vulgarization of their own research work to a larger audience, which is today’s a sub-goal to enroll young people in science & technology.

3 Pedagogy in Musicology – digital organology

As a second example, since 2021, 3rd year Bachelor students in Musicology are welcomed on the Art-Science-Technology AST platform of Grenoble INP, during 12 hours, within their *Computer Music* module. This platform has hosted for >30 years a research program, funded by C Cadoz and A Luciani, ACROE and Grenoble INP, on artistic creation engineering, and more specifically on force feedback, multisensory physics-based modeling and simulation and digital instrumentality for the arts [4].

The sessions feature lectures (explanations of haptics principles and technology, historical positioning in digital organology of Music...), hands-in demonstrations, commented listening of musical artworks created with force-feedback and physics-based modeling by various composers, such as [5], and an interview by the students of C. Cadoz (as a composer). Evaluation is based on a report, in a musicology article format.

Globally, the students develop, within their Musicology background: 1/ an understanding of the fundamental (and fundamentally new!) perspectives opened by force-feedback and physics-based simulation for digital instrumentality, music playing and composition, and more generally for creative processes; 2/ an initiation to Research, both in musical technology, and in creation in Computer Music. These two work-in-progress new pedagogical contributions are important in their Musicology training.

We are currently working towards extending this Computer Music module by implementing creative projects on the AST platform, to let the Musicology student further enact the use of force-feedback and physics-based simulation in musical creativity.

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